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Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions: A case study of SIMS

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Abstract

Higher education imparts in-depth knowledge and understanding so as to advance the students to new frontiers of knowledge in different walks of life. Higher education is seen as a process in which the students are counted as “products” absorbed in the labour market. Thus, higher education becomes input to the growth and development of business and industry. *The four* specific functions of higher education are (1) To prepare students for research and teaching; (2) To provide highly specialized training courses adapted to the needs of economic and social life; (3) To be open to all, so as to cater to the many aspects of lifelong education in the widest sense; and (4) To promote international cooperation through internationalization of research, technology, networking, and free movement of persons and scientific ideas. In this paper, we have discussed the objectives of higher education institutes, reasons to worry on quality and various factors affecting the quality of higher education. The key attributes of these quality factors are discussed and compared with the quality levels of Srinivas Institute of Management Studies (SIMS) - a higher education institution with education courses in Management, Social work, and Computer Science/Information Technology. The various quality factors considered are: (1) Curricular Aspects, (2) Teaching - Learning, Evaluation, (3) Research, Consultancy & Extension, (4) Infrastructure & learning Resource, and (5) Governance, Leadership and Management.

Keywords: Higher Education, Quality Enhancement, Quality factors

1. Introduction

The educational system is invested with the responsibility of absorbing, assimilating and delivering the new knowledge to its incumbents. Higher education imparts in-depth knowledge and understanding so as to advance the students to new frontiers of knowledge in different walks of life (subject domains). It is about knowing more and more about less and less. It develops the student’s ability to question and seek truth and makes him/her competent to critique on contemporary issues. It broadens the intellectual powers of the individual within a narrow specialization, but also gives him/her a wider perspective of the world around. Higher education therefore has become competitive. It not only matters how much in terms of quantity but how good in terms of quality that it delivers the knowledge [1].

According to Ronald Barnett [2] (1992) there are four predominant concepts of higher education:

(i) Higher education as the production of qualified human resources. In this view, higher education is seen as a process in which the students are counted as “products” absorbed in the labour market. Thus, higher education becomes input to the growth and development of business and industry.

(ii) Higher education as training for a research career. In this view, higher education is preparation for qualified scientists and researchers who would continuously develop the frontiers of knowledge. Quality within this viewpoint is more about research publications and transmission of the academic rigour to do quality research.

(iii) Higher education as the efficient management of teaching provision. Many strongly believe that teaching is the core of educational institutions. Thus, higher education institutions focus on efficient management of teaching-learning provisions by improving the quality of teaching, enabling a higher completion rate among the students.

(iv) Higher education as a matter of extending life chances. In this view, higher education is seen as an opportunity to participate in the development process of the individual through a flexible, continuing education mode.

The four specific functions of higher education are (1) To prepare students for research and teaching; (2) To provide highly specialized training courses adapted to the needs of economic and social life; (3) To be open to all, so as to cater to the many aspects of lifelong education in

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the widest sense; and (4) To promote international cooperation through internationalization of research, technology, networking, and free movement of persons and scientific ideas (UNESCO, 1996) [3]. The higher education institutes should have following objectives:

(i) Inculcating a value system in students: Although skills development is critical to the success of students in the job market, skills are of no value in the absence of an appropriate value system.

HEIs have the responsibility of inculcating a desirable value system in students. In a country like India with cultural pluralities and diversities, it is essential that students imbibe values commensurate with social, cultural, economic and environmental realities at the local, national and universal levels. There can be no dispute about inculcating core universal values like truth and right conduct, as well as the values emphasized in the various policy documents of the country. The values sown in the early stages of education, mostly aimed at cooperation and mutual understanding have to be re-emphasized in HEIs by appropriate campus experiences.

(ii) Promoting the use of technology: Most of the significant developments that one can observe today can be attributed to the impact of science and technology. While the advantages of using modern tools in day-to-day life are well recognized, the use of technology in our way of 'learning' and 'administering' leaves much to be desired. The degree of use of technological innovations in educational transactions, both academic and administrative, indicates that our system of education is still uncomfortable with new technology. At a time when our educational institutions are expected to do more with less input, they should make proper use of readily available technological innovations. Obviously, traditional methods of delivering higher education have become inadequate. To keep pace with the developments in other spheres of human endeavour, HEIs have to build on the recent technological developments and enrich the learning experiences they provide to students.

The campus community may need to be prepared adequately to make the optimum use of information and communication technologies (ICT). Conscious effort is needed to invest on hardware and to train the faculty suitably to overcome their initial reluctance in using anything new and gadget-oriented.

(iii) Fostering global competencies among students: The developments in the global scenario make it imperative for the NAAC to include in its scope of assessment the development of skills of students in India such that their skills are at par with those of their counterparts abroad. With liberalization and globalization of economic activities, the need to develop human resources of a high caliber and, consequently, the demand for higher education at nationally comparable and internationally acceptable standards has increased. While increasing access to higher education and ensuring social justice will continue to be important objectives of national development, developing internationally and inter-culturally competent human resources is of equal importance. Therefore, the HEIs should prepare students with global competencies to successfully face the changing global scenario. This requires the HEIs to be innovative, creative and entrepreneurial in their approach to skills development among students. This may involve collaborating with industries, networking with

the neighbourhood and fostering a closer relationship between the worlds of work and learning.

(iv) Contributing to national development: Most of the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) have a remarkable capacity to adapt to change, and at the same time pursue the avowed goals and

objectives they have set forth for themselves. Contributing to national development has always been a goal of Indian HEIs, explicitly or implicitly. HEIs have a significant role in building on changes to the advantage of the country and can contribute to national development, for example, by serving the cause of social justice, ensuring equity and increasing access to higher education. The HEIs should respond to the goals of national development in the changing context.

(v) Quest for excellence: While contributing to nation building and development of students, institutions should also demonstrate the drive to develop themselves into centres of excellence.

Barnett (1992) [2] quotes a 'suggestive' definition by Barrow (1991) [4] to define 'quality' in higher education: ...a high evaluation accorded to an educative process, where it has been demonstrated that, through the process, the students' educational development has been enhanced ... not only have they achieved the particular objectives set for the course but, in doing so, they have also fulfilled the general educational aims of autonomy of the ability to participate in reasoned discourse, of critical self-evaluation, and of coming to a proper awareness of the ultimate contingency of all thought and action (p. 61).

In higher education system, we have to worry on quality due to following reasons:

(1) Competition: We are entering a new regime, where competition among educational institutions for students and funds will be highly significant. With globalization and the GATS (Global Agreement on Trade in Services), the educational environment will be seized by increased competition. In order to survive in such a situation, educational institutions need to worry about their quality.

(2) Customer satisfaction: Students, parents or sponsoring agencies as customers of the educational institutions are now highly conscious of their rights or getting value for their money and time spent. They are now demanding good quality teaching and receiving employable skill sets, and thus we should constantly worry about the relevance of our courses and programmes to the needs of the labour market.

(3) Maintaining standards: As educational institutions, we are always concerned about setting our own standard and maintaining it continuously year after year. In order to maintain the standard, we should consciously make efforts to improve quality of the educational transactions as well as the educational provisions and facilities.

(4) Accountability: Every institution is accountable to its stakeholders in terms of the funds (public or private) used on it. Concern for quality will ensure accountability of the funds utilised and inform the stakeholders about taking appropriate decisions. Thus, quality can be considered as a monitoring mechanism.

(5) Improve employee morale and motivation: Your concern for quality as an institution will improve the morale and motivation of the staff in performing their duties and responsibilities. If a quality system is in place, the internal processes would be systematic making every department complementing each others service domain and helping in developing internal customer satisfaction leading to high morale and motivation.

(6) Credibility, prestige and status: If you are concerned about quality, continuously and not once in a while, it will bring in credibility to individuals and your institution because of consistency leading to prestige, status and brand value.

(7) Image and visibility: Quality institutions have the capacity to attract better stakeholder support, like getting merited students from far and near, increased donations/grants from philanthropists/funding agencies and higher employer interest for easy placement of graduates.

In this paper, we have discussed various factors affecting the quality of higher education as per the format given by National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC) of Indian Higher education quality controlling body^[5]. The key attributes of these quality factors are discussed and compared with the quality levels of Srinivas Institute of Management Studies (SIMS) - a higher education institution with education courses in Management, Social work, and Computer Science/Information Technology. The various quality factors considered are: (1) Curricular Aspects, (2) Teaching - Learning, Evaluation, (3) Research, Consultancy & Extension, (4) Infrastructure & learning Resource, and (5) Governance, Leadership and Management.

2. SIMS - An Overview:

Srinivas Institute of Management Studies (SIMS) is established with the vision of imparting quality education and expanding opportunities to all the aspirants and across all realms of knowledge. It envisages to become a centre of excellence to serve as change agent in the society by generating a pool of human resources trained in science and technology, management and social service. The college offers bachelor and master degree programmes in Business Management and Computer Science and Bachelor degree in Commerce and Masters Degree in Social Work. The vision and mission of the institute are well publicized through its website, calendar, prospectus etc. The curriculum provided for these courses are effectively improved by resorting to action planning through developing academic calendar, teaching plan, teachers diary and study material. In addition to the specialization required to be taught, the institute offers dual specialization facility of its own, and equip students to wider opportunities for employment and research. A large number of certificate programmes of short duration, customized to suit the students of all courses, are offered to promote skill development to enhance employability. Entrepreneurial talents are cultivated among the students by EDP cell. The institute offers orientation programmes, guest lectures, study tours, video lectures, field practicums, NGO internship, industrial exposures, student exchange programmes and international educational visits also as supplements to the curriculum. It supports research based learning, exposure based learning, experiential learning, event management learning, field work based learning and

laboratory based learning. Value addition is incorporated in teaching through adding extra sessions over and above the prescribed syllabus for insight development. Weak students and slow learners are supported through tutorials, counselling and mentoring.

In order to encourage research culture, a number of research centres have been constituted in the areas of expertise available with faculty in-charge of these centres. Opportunity is provided in the curriculum delivery to promote scientific thinking, spirit of questioning, expression of creative ideas, experimentation and learning by doing. Appraisal of faculty performance is done through comprehensive performance management systems and the feedback is communicated to all concerned. It is found that through this there is an increase of about 20 percent performance each year. Students appraise the faculty through a structured format on a variety of parameters. Transparency is maintained in internal assessment of students through taking into account internal examination, assignment presentations and attendance in awarding internal marks. Students with attendance shortage for genuine reasons are encouraged to attend additional classes through its innovative 'Save a year' programme. Absence from class is substantiated through declaration signed by parents. Both internal examination marks and attendance are communicated to the parents regularly by short message service (sms).

Faculty development programmes are periodically conducted. Consultancy and research are encouraged. Institution takes efforts in attracting eminent persons to visit the campus and interact with teachers and students. Most of the faculty have either secured Ph.D. or pursuing research leading to Ph.D. The institution strives to address cross cutting issues such as environment, gender etc. through conducting programmes related to the theme. Industry – institution – community interactions are maintained through village adoption, organizing job fairs, and short duration NGO internship which involve all students. Grievance committee, sexual harassment committees and anti-ragging committee have been constituted to ensure that students and staff have a hassle free life. A lot of welfare measures have been introduced for the staff of the institute. Alumni are invited as distinguished guests to chair programmes. An Alumni association has been constituted for networking, relating to placement assistance, admissions etc. Student council gives opportunity for students to elect their student representatives and participate in forum activities, annual seminars, conferences through fund raising, and sponsorship from public. College magazine, news letter and e-magazines bring out creative talent among students. The administration of the institute is decentralized.

The institute maintains high academic result at the level of 100% in P.G. Courses and more than 80% in U.G. courses. Placement cell provides career guidance to prepare the students for placements. All alumni are well settled in jobs or successful entrepreneurs managing their enterprise. Introduction of events of innovations and best practices have resulted in substantial increase in the standard of the institute to the merit requirement of an accreditation agency. During these 14 years of its efforts of preparing young men and women for challenges in life, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies sincerely tried to impart comprehensive knowledge or Samagra Jnana and actual experience of the perfection or Vijnana to its students.

3. Curriculum Planning & Implementation

Higher education institutions have to work out details for effectively operationalising the curricula. The process involves developing optimum curriculum, orientation of the teachers who would handle the curriculum and proper planning of the transaction. It also requires an understanding on the various teaching-learning practices and their appropriate use [6-7].

Since acquisition of competencies occurs at different paces for different learners it is required that the institutions have specific implementation plans identifying the time to be spent on specific components. In addition if the institution is providing specially designed courses it also has the responsibility to develop Appropriate need based curricula in consultation with stakeholders.

The Vision, Mission, Objectives & goals of the institution are made known to the students and other stakeholders through

- College website
- Prospectus
- College Calendar
- Brochure
- Alumni Association
- Students meetings
- Display boards in the college campus
- Study Materials provided to the Students

For effective implementation of the curriculum designed and provided by the affiliating university, the institution develop and deploys action plans which integrates time, quality, quantity and accountability. The key elements of the action plan are the followings:

1. **Academic Calendar** - To plan the academic year, Academic calendar is prepared every semester. The calendar reflects major events, programmes and activities to be taken up at the appropriate time.
2. **Teaching plan** – A detailed plan of the syllabus divided session-wise to ensure that time is evenly distributed for implementing the curriculum.
3. **Teachers Diary** – This is a work book maintained by each faculty wherein the particulars of each session conducted is entered with time, date, session number, topic and accessories used to ensure accountability.
4. **Study Material** – This is a compilation of relevant readings simplified and provided in thematic sequence which ensures that the entire quantity of the information prescribed for the course is conveyed.
5. **Performance Appraisal** - Periodic appraisal of the faculty make sure that they deliver the curriculum qualitatively and adequately well.

Although the institute follows the curriculum set by the University, the institute takes a proactive role through conducting curriculum improvement workshops and contributing to influence the curriculum design and development process at the University level. Feedback collected from students, alumni, academic peers, visiting faculty, resource persons for guest lectures and employers surface in these workshops. Recently, the University has consulted the college to radically redesign the obsolete syllabus of MBA program which was in vogue for 15 years and this was accomplished successfully. Similar efforts have been taken up for MCA, BCA and BBM programs. During these years the college was supplementing the curriculum deficiency through Certification programmes & Institutional Dual specialization opportunities to fill the knowledge gap between Institution and the Industry.

For effectively translating the curriculum and improving teaching practices, the University and Institution support the teachers procedurally and practically in the following ways.

1. University involves the faculty in curriculum planning and syllabus revision. Effective curriculum planning improves the capacity of the faculty to translate the curriculum into teaching.
2. The University involves the faculty in preparing question papers and valuation of answer scripts. This opportunity enriches focus on improving the teaching practices.
3. The institution frames an academic calendar for each course separately, initiated by the co-ordinator of the course, at the beginning of each semester, which helps the faculty to prepare the schedules for effective curriculum delivery and teaching.
4. Faculty development programmes are conducted by the institution to orient new faculty.
5. Faculty Improvement Programmes (FIP) are conducted periodically to acquaint faculty with improved ways of teaching and problem solving,
6. Syllabus revision exercises are conducted periodically to incorporate new knowledge and reduce redundancy.
7. Curriculum Enrichment Events (CEE) in the form of seminars and the workshops are conducted on a need basis to supplement the existing curriculum with updated knowledge.
8. Faculty are encouraged in imparting curricular innovations.
9. Use of technological gadgets are promoted.
10. Application of soft-skill in promoting curricular standards.
11. Collecting feedback from employers, industries, and alumni on improving curriculum.
12. Submitting curriculum revision suggestions to University statutory bodies.

Apart from the above, the contribution made by the institution for effective curriculum delivery and transaction on the curriculum provided by the affiliating University include the following :

- Extensive library facility – Separate library for different departments functioning on extended hours with book bank facility and open access Facility.
- Well equipped computer lab with 150 networked computers and peripherals connected to internet are installed in the Laboratory and accessible to faculty and the students.
- Internal Examinations, student presentations and assignments are regular features of teaching.
- Seminars, workshops and guest lectures on curriculum related topics are conducted periodically.
- The necessary infrastructure conducive to effective curriculum delivery are available. This includes a 200 seater fully air-conditioned gallery hall, classrooms with sophisticated and comfortable furniture, 600 seater Auditorium facility for mega programmes and a 1300 capacity open theatre.
- The modern gadgets which are the vital part of effective curriculum delivery such as Amplifiers, LCD projectors are fixed in all classrooms.

For effective operationalisation of the curriculum, the institution networks with different industries, Research bodies, Universities and other agencies :

- Industry visits are part of MBA and BBM courses. Students presents the reports of the industrial visits in the class and submit for evaluation.
- Short projects focusing on investigation through research methodology are undertaken by the students in industries are part of the fulfillment of the course requirement. In many cases the topic of the research study will be based on the interest of the agency where they are placed.
- Summer Placement : Opportunity to gain exposure to industry is obtained through doing placement during mid summer holidays.
- Experts from the industry visit the institution on invitation and give guest lectures which enhances the ties and networking between the industry and the institution.
- Developing software in the form of micro-projects are part of the course for BCA and MCA students. This networking helps mutual benefits.
- Regular fieldwork is part of the curriculum for MSW and students spend half the duration of the entire course in various voluntary and social organizations which improves the networking with the institution.

The generally accepted frequency of curriculum revision is once in five years, but it may pre-poned to two or three years. There has been change in the syllabus for the courses such as BBM, BCA, MCA and MSW during the last two years. The following curriculum improvements were proposed by the institution :

(1) Contribution of the Institution :

- Students shall present a compulsory seminar in each semester.
- The internal assessment marks for each paper may be raised.
- One choice based paper shall be introduced for master degree programmes.
- The evaluation of field practicum for MSW should be done both internally, and externally through a viva conducted by external examiner.

(2) Contribution of the Staff :

- The college is represented in the Board Of Studies, Doctoral committee, and the Board of Examiners of the University.

(3) Student Feedback :

- Curriculum and its relevance to job market requirements form subject of discussion in meetings held with the alumni.

(4) Stakeholder Feedback :

- Academic peers consult very often on curriculum improvement.
- Employers, community and parents invest preference for high profile curriculum and university tries to live up to this expectations.
- Employers send their representatives to the college for guest lectures, functions, etc. and they comment on the curricular standards followed.

Parents of the students and community at large expect quality education and supply feedback on the achievements of their wards on the curriculum offered through the form of courses.

4. Academic Flexibility

Keeping in mind the growing needs at state, national and global level the institution imparts education at Graduate/Post Graduate Degree level in Business Management/Commerce, Computer Science and Social Work. The list of Courses offered by the Institution is given in table 1.

Table 1: List of Courses offered by the Institution

S. No.	Program Offered	No. of Intake	Affiliation & Recognition
1	BBM	150	Mangalore University
2	BCA	150	Mangalore University
3	B.Com	75	Mangalore University
4	MBA	120	Mangalore University & AICTE
5	MCA	60	Mangalore University & AICTE
6	MSW	120	Mangalore University

The institution is a unique affiliated college under the University offering a variety of certificate programmes and skill development programmes to its regular students meant to enrich the competitiveness and employability. The various certificate programmes offered for our MBA, MCA, MSW, BBM, BCA, and B.Com courses and its goals and objectives are listed in tables 2 - 7.

Table 2: Certificate programmes offered for MBA Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Certificate Course in Online investment	Mastering in Share market investment	To identify the investment potentials & Methods	05 days
2	Certificate Course on Quantitative Analysis using MATLAB/OCTAVE	Familiarizing modern analysis techniques	Simplifying research analysis & interpretation	05 days
3	Certificate Course on Investment Banking	Mastering in Banking investment	To know various banking services for investors	05 days
4	Certificate Course in Cloud Computing	Developing expertise in modern IT applications	To learn and adopt latest IT Application models	05 days
5	Certificate Course in Android Mobile Applications	Involvement in software development through innovativeness	Developing customized applications for open source Android operating system	05 days
6	Certificate Course in Retail Marketing & Brand Management	Develop competency in retail marketing	To know various strategies of retail marketing	05 days
7	Certificate Course in SPSS/SPSS Statistical Software	Usage of statistical software in Research	To simplify enormous data and generate reports	05 days
8	Certificate Course in Computer Applications (Tally, Excel & Access)	Usage of basic Accounting & Business application software	To create, tables, graphs, and business reports	05 days
9	Certificate Course in R-Statistical Computing for Business Analytics	To understand and expertise in business analytics	Decision making through manipulation of enormous data generated in business	05 days

			environment	
10	Certificate Course in Animation & Visual Effects	Use of creative thinking in business presentations	Learn animation techniques	05 days
11	Certificate Course on Mobile Business & Mobile banking	Use of mobile devices in Business transactions	To learn various mobile technology, models and security aspects in mobile transactions	05 days
12	Certificate Course in Blue Ocean Strategy & Green Business	Specialize in monopoly business	Develop strategies in competition free business	05 days

Table 3: Certificate programmes offered for MCA Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Certificate Course in Animation & Visual Effects	Use of Creative thinking in Business Presentations	Learn Animation Techniques	5-6 Days
2	Strategic Management in IT Sector	Build successful business strategies	Develop Capability in Strategic Management	5-6 Days
3	Certificate Course in Enterprises Resource Planning	To develop successful resource planners	Resource Mobilization for Enterprises	05 days
4	Certificate Course in Entrepreneurship Development	Build talented enterprisers	Developing entrepreneurial leadership	05 days
5	Certificate Course on R-Statistical Computing & Graphics for Business Analysis	Use of Specialized techniques for business analysis	Familiarity with R-Statistical Computing and graphics	05 days
6	Certificate Course on Cyber Law & IT Security	Ensuring improved cyber security expertise	Understanding of cyber laws and IT security	05 days

Table 4: Certificate programmes offered for MSW Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Certificate Course in HRD	To become effective managers	To understand the mechanisms & processes in developing Human Resources	05 days
2	Certificate Course in Counseling	Preparing individuals as effective Counselors	Emotional support & Problem solving	05 days
3	Certificate Course in Human Rights	Awareness of freedom of individuals	Identify obstacles in exercising freedom	05 days
4	Certificate Course in NGO Management	To improve the functional efficacy of NGOs	To provide better professionals to work in NGO's	05 days
5	Certificate Course in Industrial & Labour Laws	To maintain peace & Harmony in industry	To operate within legal framework	05 days

Table 5: Certificate programmes offered for BBM Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Certificate Course in Spreadsheet Techniques	Use of various spreadsheet applications	Knowing various techniques in spreadsheet applications	05 days
2	Certificate Course in E-Business Website Development	To design business websites	To know various software used in dynamic business website & add new features	05 days
3	Certificate Course in Business Communication & Soft skills	To improve functional effectiveness in Management	Enhancement of better use of skills	05 days
4	Certificate Course in Linux & Open Source Software	Comprehensive idea of all open source software	Learning Linux based software applications	05 days
5	Certificate Course in Animation & Visual Effect	Develop competency in business presentations	To learn and use creativity in Animation & Visual effects	05 days

Table 6: Certificate programmes offered for BCA Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Certificate Course in Animation & Visual Effect	Develop competency in business presentations	To learn and use creativity in Animation & Visual effects	05 days
2	Certificate Course in Hardware & Networking	Assembling the computers & other devices	Knowledge in proper alignment of computer hardware	05 days
3	Certificate Course in E-Business Website development	To design business websites	To know various software used in dynamic business website & add new features	05 days
4	Certificate Course in Tally Accounting Software	To know use of computer software in Accounting	Elementary computer based accounting practices	05 days
5	Certificate Course in Linux & Open Source Software	Comprehensive idea of all open source software	Learning Linux based software applications	05 days
6	Certificate Course on Spoken English & Interview Techniques	To improve functional effectiveness in Management	Enhancement of better use of skills	05 days

Table 7: Certificate programmes offered for B.Com Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Certificate Course in Computer Applications	Use of various spreadsheet applications	Knowing various techniques in spreadsheet applications	05 days
2	Certificate Course in Tally Accounting Software	To know use of computer software in Accounting	Elementary computer based accounting practices	05 days
3	Certificate Course on Spoken English & Soft skills	To improve functional effectiveness in Management	Enhancement of better use of skills	05 days
4	Certificate Course in Linux & Open Source Software	Comprehensive idea of all open source software	Learning Linux based software applications	05 days

Several skill development courses devised and offered by the institution for the various programmes of study such as MBA, MCA, MSW, BBM, BCA, B.Com. and are listed in tables 8 to table 13.

Table 8: Skill development courses devised and offered by the institution for MBA Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Fund rising	Successful program implementation	Financial resource mobilization	2 - 3 Days
2	Innovative Ideas in marketing	Capturing market	Device competitive strategies	2 - 3 Days
3	Business Communication	Winning business	Overtaking competitors	2 - 3 Days
4	Effective Presentation	Selling the Idea	Improved competitiveness	2 - 3 Days
5	Problem solving	Appropriate solutions	Better Judgment	2 - 3 Days
6	Team Building	Synergy	Better Collaboration	2 - 3 Days
7	Entrepreneurship & Small business planning	To be once own master	Alternate employment avenues	2 - 3 Days

Table 9: Skill development courses devised and offered by the institution for MCA Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Application Software Development	Expertise in Application software	Fast develop application software	2 - 3 Days
2	Website Development and Design Skill	Developing an attractive website	Applying new techniques in Website development	2 - 3 Days
3	Fund Raising Skill	Successful program implementation	Financial resource mobilization	2 - 3 Days
4	Team Presentation Skill	Effective Interaction in teams	Better communication	2 - 3 Days
5	Trouble shooting skills	Identifying Fault	Quick response	2 - 3 Days
6	Android Application Development	Developing new Mobile Phone applications	Catering to the varied users group	2 - 3 Days

Table 10: Skill development courses devised and offered by the institution for MSW Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Business Correspondence	Managerial Efficiency	Improved communication	2 - 3 Days
2	Spoken English	Power of convincing	Improved expression	5 Days
3	Public speaking	Developing Command	Gaining attention	5 Days
4	Programme organizing	Successful program implementation	Organizational skills	2 - 3 Days
5	Personality Building	Key to success	Organizing oneself	2 - 3 Days

Table 11: Skill development courses devised and offered by the institution for BBM Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Time Management	Best use of available time	Time Conscious	2 - 3 Days
2	Communication skills	Improved teamwork	Best understood	2 - 3 Days
3	Leadership Skills	Self Starter	Developing Initiative	2 - 3 Days
4	Human Relationship skills	Working with People	Placing importance on human resource	2 - 3 Days
5	Soft Skills	Successful leader	Winning support	2 - 3 Days

Table 12: Skill development courses devised and offered by the institution for BCA Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Time Management	Best use of available time	Time Conscious	2 - 3 Days
2	Communication skills	Improved teamwork	Best understood	2 - 3 Days
3	Leadership Skills	Self Starter	Developing Initiative	2 - 3 Days
4	Human Relationship skills	Working with People	Placing importance on human resource	2 - 3 Days
5	Soft Skills	Successful leader	Winning support	2 - 3 Days

Table 13: Skill development courses offered by the institution for B.Com. Programme

S. No.	Name of the Course	Goals	Objectives	Duration
1	Time Management	Best use of available time	Time Conscious	2 - 3 Days
2	Communication skills	Improved teamwork	Best understood	2 - 3 Days
3	Leadership Skills	Self Starter	Developing Initiative	2 - 3 Days
4	Human Relationship skills	Working with People	Placing importance on human resource	2 - 3 Days
5	Soft Skills	Successful leader	Winning support	2 - 3 Days

Various institutional provisions with reference to academic flexibility and its helpful to students in terms of skills development, academic mobility, progression to higher studies and improved potential for employability are discussed below :

(1) **Range of Core /Elective options offered by the University and those opted by the college :** Range of core/elective options offered by the University as per its curriculum and those opted by the college are listed in table 14.

Table 14: Range of core/elective options offered by the University as per its curriculum and those opted by the college

Sl. No.	Name of Course	No. of Electives	Names of Electives	No. of Electives offered in the past 5 years
1	MBA	20	1. Strategic Financial Management & Policy	12
			2. Security Analysis & Portfolio Management	
			3. Human Resource Development	
			4. Industrial Relations	
			5. Marketing Research & Consumer Behaviour	
			6. Promotion and Distribution Management	
			7. Financial Services	
			8. International Financial Management	
			9. Global Human Resource Management	
			10. Labour Laws	
			11. International Marketing Management	
			12. Service Marketing	
2	MCA	1	1. Systems Administration	1
3	MSW	4	1. Research Project	4
			2. Disaster Management	
			3. Women & Gender Equity	
			4. Social Policy & Planning	
4	BBM	2	1. Marketing	2
			2. HRM/Finance	
5	BCA	2	1. Computer Oriented Numerical Analysis	2
			2. System Analysis and Design	
6	B.Com.	5	1. Human Resource Management	2
			2. Advanced Banking	
			3. Business Taxation	
			4. Computer Application	
			5. Insurance	

(2) Choice Based Credit System and range of subject options

The college is offering choice based credit system for MBA and MSW courses. The students can take a choice based paper in the third semester of their course. Out of a range of subject options,

students are encouraged to choose any subject in any college under University or in the University department. Under this model, many students from other colleges are attending the choice based paper offered by the college as shown in table 15.

Table 15: Choice based credit subjects offered by the college under affiliated University.

S. No.	Name of the Course	Choice based Subject
1	MBA	1 out of 25 Approved Subjects
2	MSW	1 out of 25 Approved Subjects
3	MCA	Not Applicable
4	BBM	Not Applicable
5	BCA	Not Applicable
6	B.Com.	Not Applicable

(3) Courses offered in modular form

Modular courses are provided unit wise and are arranged at department level by academic committees comprising of HOD's,

staff and Principal. The training programs offered in modular form under all the three P.G. Courses are listed in tables 16 - 18.

Table 16: Training programs offered in modular form for MBA Course

S. No.	Name of Training Program	Objectives	Duration
1	Programming in Linux & Open Source Software	Reducing dependency on paid software	2-3 Days
2	Business Law & Corporate Law	To learn legal framework of Business	2-3 Days
3	KASH Enrichment Programs	Upgrading Performance through enhanced perception	2-3 Days
4	Hands on training in E-Commerce website design & Maintenance	Firsthand experience in website design	2-3 Days
5	Training on Soft skills & Business Communication	Acquiring mastering in interpersonal relationship	One Hour per week

Table 17: Training programs offered in modular form for MCA Course

S. No.	Name of Training Program	Objectives	Duration
1	Training on International certification in SUN Certified JAVA professional	To know better on a new Programming Language	2-3 Days
2	Training on International certification in ORACLE Certified professional	To enhance the skills of using ORACLE as database program	2-3 Days
3	Training on Nanotechnology & Quantum Computing	To catch up with fast changing technology	2-3 Days
4	Intensive Training on Linux & Open Source Software	Reducing dependency on paid software	2-3 Days
5	Intensive training on Business communication & Soft skills	Acquiring mastering in interpersonal relationship	One Hour per week
6	KASH Enrichment Training	Upgrading Performance through enhanced perception	One Hour per week

Table 18: Training programs offered in modular form for MSW Course

S. No.	Name of Training/ Workshop Program	Objectives	Duration
1	Book Review Techniques	Mastering techniques for better book review	2-3 Days
2	Essay writing Practice	Summarization & Presentation of Topic based text	2-3 Days
3	Gender Sensitization	Develop Pro-active attitude & gender equity	2-3 Days
4	Integration of News Clippings	Learning ideas through collage	2-3 Days
5	Character & Spiritual Development	Healthy Character formation	2-3 Days

(4) Lateral and vertical mobility within and across programmes and courses

Lateral entry provision exists in some programs of University such as MCA, B.Com. etc. and the institute is extending that facility to its students.

(5) Enrichment courses

Several short term enrichment programmes are offered to the students by the college which include, courses on Linux and Open Source software usage, courses on Derivatives, Excel applications, Digital marketing, Personality development, Interview skills, KASH (**K**nowledge, **A**ttitude, **S**kill and **H**abit) enrichment training course etc.

(6) Value Added Chapters in all Subjects

Apart from the University syllabus for each subject, the college has added a value added chapter of 3-5 sessions in all subjects in the Teaching Plan. This is intended to be taught as value enrichers to the curriculum. Unlike University syllabus, the topics under the value added chapter can be modified/changed every year depending on latest developments in the subject.

(7) Credit transfer and accumulation facility

There are no transfer and accumulation facilities offered.

5. Curriculum Enhancement

Institutions goals and objectives are focused on enhancing knowledge, skills and readiness to be absorbed in the job

market. By keeping this in mind, the institution supplement the University's curriculum by variety of means:

- Curriculum delivery & pedagogy
- Skill development Package
- Exposure visits
- Certification Programmes
- Workshops
- Employability Trainings
- Industry-Institution Interface Programmes
- Field Visits
- Seminars & Conferences
- Guest Lectures
- Programmes under "Vivekananda Study Circle"
- NPTEL Video Lecture
- Value Addition Classes
- Imparting Messages Celebration of National/International Days
- Encouragement to take up EdX University Programs

(1) Curriculum delivery & pedagogy

The academic curriculum of the University in respect of all the courses is imparted systematically and well structured through:

- Session wise teaching plan
- Comprehensive study material prepared exactly according to the syllabus.
- Periodic internal Examination
- Topic based assignments

- Student presentations
- Case study analysis
- Student feedback
- Research Projects
- Field Practicum
- Laboratory based Practicals
- Thematic Fest
- Forum Activities

These activities/models enriches the curriculum set by the University and helps to integrate the institutions goals and objectives.

(2) Skill development Package

The following skill development programmes offered as a package as part and parcel with the curriculum :

- Fund Raising
- Innovative ideas in Marketing
- Business Communication
- Effective Presentation
- Problem solving
- Team Building
- Entrepreneurship & Small business Planning
- Application software development Skill
- Website development & Design Skill
- Fund Raising Skill
- Team Presentation Skill
- Troubleshooting Skills
- Android Application Development Skills
- Business Correspondence
- Spoken English
- Public speaking
- Program organizing
- Personality Building
- Time Management
- Communication Skills
- Leadership Skills
- Human Relationship Skills
- Soft Skills

(3) Exposure visits

The college provides opportunity for exposure visit to gain first-hand knowledge. Some of them are :

- Orientation programmes
- Industry visits
- Study tours
- International educational visits
- Student exchange programmes

(4) Certification Programmes :

The college is conducting various certificate programmes to bridge the gap between University curriculum and industry requirements. Some of the certificate programmes which are regular in feature are listed below:

(a) MBA Program

- Certificate course in Online Investment
- Certificate course on quantitative analysis using MATLAB/OCTAVE
- Certificate course on Investment Banking
- Certificate course in Cloud computing
- Certificate course in Android Mobile Applications
- Certificate course in Retail Marketing & Brand Management

- Certificate course in SPSS /PSPP statistical software
- Certificate Course in Computer Application (Tally, Excel, & Access)
- Certificate Course in R-Statistical Computing for Business Analytics
- Certificate Course in Blue Ocean Strategy and Green Business
- Certificate Course in Animation & Visual Effects
- Certificate Course on Mobile Business & Mobile banking

(b) MCA Program

- Certificate course in Animation & Visual Effects
- Certificate course in Strategic management in IT Sector
- Certificate course in Enterprises Resource Planning
- Certificate course in Entrepreneurial Development Programme
- Certificate course in R – Statistical Computing & Graphics for Business Analytics
- Certificate course in Cyber Law & IT security

(c) MSW Program

- Certificate course in HRD
- Certificate course in Counseling
- Certificate course in Human Rights
- Certificate course in NGO Management
- Certificate course in Industrial & Labour Laws

(d) BBM, BCA, B.Com Programs

- Certificate course in Spread Sheet Techniques
- Certificate course in E-Business Website Development
- Certificate course in Business & Communication soft skills
- Certificate course in Linux & Open Source Software
- Certificate course in Hardware & Networking
- Certificate course in Tally – Accounting software
- Certificate course in Animation

(5) Workshops

The institution organizes workshops of varying duration for all the courses of study. This will supplement the University curriculum gap with the institutions goals and objectives. A list of such workshops is listed below :

(a) MBA Program

- Workshop for preparing ICWA Aspirants
- Workshop on Corporate Yoga & Mind Control
- Workshop on Business Etiquettes
- Workshop on Nanotechnology Commercialization & Business Opportunities
- Workshop on Disaster Management
- Workshop on ERP Modules Applications & Vendors
- Workshop on Mobile Business & Mobile Banking

(b) MCA Program

- Workshop in Android Operating System & Application Development
- Workshop on PHP and MySQL
- Workshop on Stress Management
- Workshop on Cloud Computing
- Workshop on E-Business website development

- Workshop on Quantitative Analysis using MATLAB/OCTAVE

(c) MSW Program

- Workshop on Book Review Techniques
- Workshop on Essay Writing Practice
- Workshop on Gender sensitization
- Workshop on News Clippings Analysis & Integration
- Workshop for Character & Spiritual Development

(6) Employability Trainings

- Competitive exam training
- Interview preparedness
- Effective Decision making
- SWOT Analysis
- Oral & Written Communication
- Problem Solving
- Work Ethics

(7) Industry-Institution Interface Programmes

Various programmes are planned, implemented and promoted for Industry-Institution Interface.

- Industry Projects
- Guest lectures by Industry Experts
- Campus Recruitment
- Summer Placement
- Block Placement
- Mentorship Programs by Industry Managers
- Round Table Interaction with Entrepreneurs & Industry Experts
- Stories of Successful Entrepreneurs
- Development of Industry related Business cases
- Consultancy services

(8) Field Visits

- Orientation Visits
- Community Surveys
- Regular Field Practicum
- Social service activities

(9) Programmes under “Vivekananda Study Circle” :

- Awareness Programmes on various social, moral, ethical principles
- Special lectures to instill moral and ethical values in life

(10) NPTEL Video Lecture

NPTEL Video lectures on Business Management, Social Science and Computer Science & IT are shown to the students periodically to enrich and supplement the University Curriculum.

(11) Value Addition Classes

Each theory paper has an extra chapter at the end, focusing on value building which is beyond the limits of curriculum offered by the University.

(12) Imparting Messages by Celebration of National/International Days

Days such as International Water Day, Health Day, Mothers day, Environment day, Human Rights day, Climate day etc. are observed through conducting talks & community awareness processions.

(13) Encouragement to take up edX University Programs

In order to enhance global competencies, the Institution encourages its students and faculty members to take up various Free video online courses from edX University which is a Joint Venture of Harvard University & MIT.

The following are the efforts made by the institution to modify, enrich and organize the curriculum to enhance the experience of the students with needs of the dynamic employment market

- **Case Study Development:** Students are given opportunity to extract real life context from organizations where they visit either for field practicum of research project work or summer placement and these are worked out into case studies through group exercises under the guidance of the faculty supervisors. This enables to enrich and organize the curriculum beyond routine classroom learning through lecture, and improve the dynamism and competitiveness of the students in the employment market.
- **Group Discussions:** Topics of monotonous nature are divided to be discussed among students in groups and generate ideas in line with their experience and viewpoints. These discussions are guided by the faculty to retain the curriculum relevance. Ultimately, group presentations lead to encouragement of students initiatives and leadership qualities which are the focus in the employment markets.
- **Simulation:** Efforts are made to utilize simulation techniques to reproduce real life situations in classroom. Students develop ability for positive responses in problem solving and decision making.
- **Laboratory based learning:** Students are encouraged to utilize various Application software in computer laboratory. They are also trained to develop reports using various statistical analysis and data management & interpretation packages through network based learning.
- **Field work based learning:** Fieldwork has the potential to enrich the curriculum combining the experiences of the students with concept based theoretical learning. This takes place in the following ways :
 1. Discussion with industry expert
 2. Data collection/information gathering in the process of research project preparation.
- **Exposure based learning:** Through study tour, industry visits and interaction with resource persons. exposure based learning will provide the techniques of resource mobilization, quality production, marketing strategies, customer satisfaction and Human resource management in business.
- **Research based Learning:** Undertaking research projects as part of course requirement enables students with adequate know-how on application of alternative solutions to social context.
- **Experiential Learning:** Students of both UG and PG programmes conduct programs such as marketing exhibition, Online virtual investment, Business model competitions, and group discussion. Programs such as Manegma – National Level Conference on selected Themes of Business Management, MAGMA-Management Feast, MATRIX- International Business Case Presentation, MEGA-INDIA – Indian Industry Study, Manthana – An Intellectual churning of Social work Fraternity, ESPERANZA – An IT Fest, etc.

- **Student Forum Based Activities :** Various student forums like HR Forum, Marketing Forum, Finance Forum, IT Forum are also providing opportunity for students to creatively reflect their experiences and integrating with it curriculum.
- **Entrepreneurship Development Cell:** A separate cell for entrepreneurship development is incorporated in the college. This cell creates awareness of need and relevance of entrepreneurship as career option among the students thereby strengthening their Entrepreneurship skills.
- **Team Work Activities:** Students of the College plan and organize various social programs like Teachers Day Celebration, Onam Celebration, Iftar Party, Karnataka Rajyothsava etc.
- **Idea Creation through Marketing Exhibition:** MBA, BBM and B.Com students involve in creating new business models/Ideas in Teams of 4-5 students and present their model in Marketing Exhibition conducted by the respective Departments. This kind of practical learning through Idea creation leads to innovation in business models/marketing Ideas.

The institution made efforts to integrate the cross cutting issues such as Gender, Climate Change, Environmental Education, Human Rights, ICT etc., into the curriculum. Some of them are :

- Apart from the syllabi each individual subject provides sessions for value additions. This is integrated into the teaching plan of each subject. This includes cross-cutting issues relating to gender, environment, human rights, social justice, various business strategies etc.
- Workshops are conducted periodically on topic such as Women education, Women Rights, Atrocities on Women, Dowry problem, Child Labour, to integrate Gender Sensitization into the curriculum.
- Social service activities such as Tree Planting also called Vanamahotsava, Plastic Free Campus, Cleanliness campaign, etc. integrate environmental education into the curriculum. In the Bachelor Degree programs of certain courses, environmental education is being taught.
- Constitution and Human Rights are being taught as a part of the curriculum. Certificate course on Human Right is also imparted. Students conduct various programmes such as Street Play in the community highlighting Human Rights Issues.

The college gives emphasis to computer based information and communication technology for all courses either through inclusion in the curriculum or through specialized certificate programmes or through exposure and training based skill development.

- In BCA program, information and communication technology is the integral part of the syllabus. In the course, the students will study hardware and assembling techniques, software including operating systems and application software packages. Along with these, students will also study computer networking, web designing, data communication and database management systems and multimedia systems.
- In BBM syllabus, students are taught Computer applications as a paper in which the students are exposed to hardware and software of the computers. They will also study computer networking and various business application packages like MS Word, MS PowerPoint, MS Excel and database software like MS Access. The

students are offered an additional 5 hours certificate program by the college on TALLY – accounting software. Students are encouraged to utilize the communication technology lab to upgrade their technical skills.

- Being a specialized course on computer based communication technology, MCA students master on all aspects of computer science and information technology in detail/depth over a period of three years.
- MSW students are equipped with computer based communication technology through Word processing, PowerPoint presentations, spreadsheet skills for their project report preparation.
- MBA students invariably utilize the laptop computers to access the business information through wireless internet connections provided by the college. Apart from using the basic computer communication technology, the department offers the following certification courses of varying durations in parallel with normal course of study for availing information related to business intelligence for better analysis and decision making. A list of such certification programs as value addition are mentioned below :

(1) Accounting Through TALLY, (2) Statistical Analysis through SPSS (3) Computer for Managers (4) E-Business & Mobile Business Technology (5) Business Intelligence Using MatLab.

The following value-added courses/enrichment programmes offered to ensure holistic development of students :

- (1) Workshop on Character and Spiritual development are conducted periodically. A tie-up with Sri Ramakrishna Mutt, Mangalore provides opportunity for students to involve in the programmes conducted by Mutt.
- (2) The college is also conducting a certificate course on Yoga & Mind control for enhancing the moral & ethical values of students.
- (3) Programs such as Public Speaking, Personality Building, Spoken English, Program Organizing, Team Building improve the life skills and contribute to holistic development of students.
- (4) A variety of certificate programs and Dual specializations focusing vertically on chosen specializations and horizontally in related areas, improve the career options and enhance the employability of the students. The Placement cell offers programs such as mock interviews, Group discussions, Talent Identification, Organizational Opportunity Presentation.
- (5) Programmes are conducted by the students in the community to improve their social conditions and resources and facilities available from various sources create community orientation among the students. Rural camps are conducted in the community where students live along with the community people and develop insights into their problems.
- (6) The National Service scheme unit of the college has regular activities in community service.
- (7) A certificate course on NGO management, provides enhanced knowledge on community development.
- (8) The college has its own NGO called **SIRRA** – (Srinivas Institute of Rural Reconstruction Agency) which promotes community activity involving students in areas such as Education, Health, Environment and Livelihood.
- (9) The institution has designed several programs under **“Vivekananda Study Circle** “in collaboration with Ramakrishna Mutt. The College conducted a number of

awareness programs on various social, moral, ethical values and ways of life to students and public. The Students are also motivated by special lectures to instill moral and ethical values in them.

The institution monitors and evaluate the quality of its enrichment programmes as follows :

1. The college oversees the implementation of the enrichment programs through all the faculties headed by the coordinators of the respective departments.
2. Student placement, success in competitive exams, academic achievements, student feedback, employer feedback, community response, peer group assessment serves to monitor and evaluate the quality of enrichment programs.
3. The institution awards certificate of merit on completion of respective certification/skill/training courses to ensure consistency in implementation and monitor the quality of the programs.

6. Feedback System

The generally accepted frequency of syllabus revision is once in five years, but it may be postponed to two or three years. The basis for revision is introducing new topics and subjects and updating to contemporary relevance. During curriculum revisions, the senior faculty attends the deliberations, voice changes required for appropriate inclusion. The college directly involves in the revision and the preparation of curriculum through offering modifications and suggestions. There has been change in the syllabus for the courses offered by the institute such as BBM, BCA, MCA and MSW for the last two years. The following changes have been introduced which were suggested/ supported by the college :

- Students have to present a seminar for 25 marks made compulsory in each semester.
- The internal assessment marks for each paper was raised from 20 to 30.
- One choice based paper was introduced in lieu of a common paper for Master Degree programmes.
- The evaluation of field practicum for MSW has been done through internal assessment and through a viva in the presence of external examiner.
- In case of MBA Course, the college is continuously requesting the University to upgrade the syllabus frequently. This year the College has designed & developed a draft syllabus for MBA program, which is in par with the syllabus of International Business schools and waiting for its recognition & Implementation.
- Similarly, the MSW department of the College conducted meeting of faculty from MSW colleges of Mangalore University to suggest changes in the syllabus to be submitted BOS.

All courses are customized to enhance employability to those who pass out and placement percentages give an indirect idea of the curriculum relevance to the job market. Nevertheless Institute collects feedback on curriculum through the following mechanisms

- Curriculum and its relevance to job market requirements form subject of discussion in meetings held with the alumni. Therefore alumni form a major source of feedback.
- Academic peers both in closer & wider circle such as those from other colleges affiliated under the same University and those working in different University both within (National level) and outside the country (International level) consult very often. They reflect on

the relevance and the improvements on an up to date basis.

- Employers, community and parents invest preference for high profile curriculum and university tries to live up to this expectations.
- Employers send their representative for the activities of the college such as guest lectures, college functions, judges for events etc. and they involve in the curricular standards followed. This also forms a source for feedback.
- Parents of the students and community at large expect quality education and supply feedback on the achievements of their wards attained through the curriculum offered in the various courses.
- Students fill up a feedback form at the end of each semester evaluate their teachers and voice their option on curriculum.

7. Conclusion

1. The vision, mission and objectives of the institution, are communicated to the students, teachers, staff and other stakeholders.
2. The institution develops and deploys action plans for effective implementation of the curriculum.
3. Teachers receive support (procedural and practical) for effectively translating the curriculum and improving teaching practices.
4. The institution ensures effective curriculum delivery and transaction.
5. 5. The institution interact with beneficiaries such as industry, research bodies and the university for effective operationalisation of the curriculum.
6. Institution has mechanisms to analyze /ensure that the stated objectives of curriculum are achieved in the course of implementation.
7. The institution offers a number of program options leading to different degrees.
8. The curriculum offers a number of elective options / Choice Based Credit System (CBCS).
9. A number of new programs and program combinations are available to meet the needs of the students and the society.
10. Options are available to students for acquiring additional skills and supplementary / enrichment courses along with their regular curricula.
11. The institution follows a semester system.
12. The institution revises the curriculum at regular intervals and analyses the impact.
13. The curriculum provides adequate scope for introducing programmes in emerging thrust areas/interdisciplinary areas.
14. The institution takes initiative in supplementing the University's Curriculum.
15. Institution integrates the cross cutting issues such as Gender, Climate Change, Environmental Education, Human Rights, ICT etc., into the curriculum.
16. Institution enriches and organizes the curriculum to enhance the experiences of the students to cope with the needs of the employment market.
17. All learners have access to value-added programmes, including communication skills / soft skills.
18. Institution monitors and evaluates the quality of the enrichment programmes being offered.

19. Structured feedback from students is an essential component in the curricular design and development process.
20. Structured feedback from stakeholders and students is obtained for enriching the curriculum.
21. The institution draws on the feedback from national and international faculty.
22. Inputs from affiliated colleges are an essential part of the feedback system.

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